

Research Article

A Study on the Plot Creation of the Novella “A Recommendation Letter”

Nan San Htwe(Liu Zhimei)^{1,2*}

¹Department of Chinese, Lecturer ,University of Foreign Languages, Mandalay, Myanmar

²Modern Literature. Department of Literature, PhD student (Student No.201607110200001), Art College , Hubei University, Wuhan, China

***Corresponding Author**

Accepted: 20 July, 2020; Online: 10 August, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3978744>

Abstract: *This paper mainly presents about the skill of plot creation of the novella called “A Recommendation Letter”. The novella called “A Recommendation Letter” is from the collections of novella and it was written to increase life knowledge for social life problem among struggling social situation and to be perceptive merits of the parents. It is learnt from the point of plot creation by doing research.*

Keywords: *plot, plot creation, techniques of plot creation*

Introduction

The novella called “A Recommendation Letter” was written by Myanmar born Chinese writer Xu. It is about turning to a good man after relinquishing gambling, a bad habit, by perceiving merits of the parents in the struggling social life context. With belated remorse merging imaginatively from experiences and witnesses of the writer, becoming a good man by having right view was arranged as the events and written. The skill of plot creation of the novella called “A Recommendation Letter” is presented in the current study and it is aimed to be supportive in the learning area of plot.

Materials and methods

Since novellas are composed basing on practical context (real event), it contains good and bad events of the nature of the world and nature of humans. Readers appeal to novellas is occurring since the events are written as those in real context by creating plots descriptively to be the same pattern when novellas were written. Writer Xu’s novella can give readers attractions

towards the plot from start to end. The plot structure is concise and mean, and it also describes with one good scene. Regarding with readers' appeal to the novellas, Sayar Zaw Gyi said that,

"I want to say that there is the ability of creating appealing notices and restraints on good and bad about human's nature changing human's world in term of trend, and events."

Events created by plots and human's natures in novellas arises charm pleasure and pleasures making life potency for readers.

With the writers' craft, by connecting with some events, it is a kind of writing intending for appealing of the readers. The story of the novel is the writing with likable acts based on plot structure. The plot structure is the events written by logical sequence heading to its aim.

1. Plot Creation

The skill of plot creation is employed to take readers' mindfulness from start to end while novel is reading. Relating to the skill of plot creation as an importance of being a good novel, Thuriyu Ka Ni Ta said that

"Making plot structure, twists in novels, the flow of events in novel, smooth logical sequence can be said the devices of novels. That making plot structure, event twists, the flow of events in novel, smooth logical sequence can produce good prose which leads to a good novel. How better the basic aims of the novels, a good novel cannot be produced if these devices are not well manipulated. In writing a novel, on the condition that grammatical ornaments, the usage of words, beautifying by sound devices, beautifying the meanings by allusive embellishment are not flexible and being flaws, a good novel cannot be produced if the above mentioned devices of novels are not practiced well."

The aim of the writers attached with goodwill will be effective with creations such as good composition, well presentation, and good creation of plot.

Novel writers use plot creation in order to be a good novel.

- A. Techniques on plot creation
- B. Events sequencing
- C. Composition in detail

2. Plot Creation of the novella: “A Recommendation Letter”

In the novella ““A Recommendation Letter”, the writer aimed to be aware becoming on the right tract by getting right opinion and perceiving merits of the parents after the mother has passed away in struggling social life context, and to educate perceiving merits of the parents after their passing away.

The writer stationed an aim based on plot, events, and characters in writing the novel. From the aim, plot, events and characters produced from plot and events are written in detail. By that sequence, a novel can be written.

To reveal the aim vividly, the writer accustoms to use different techniques. Regarding with that view, Catherine, Morner and Rausch said

“Images, movements, symbols and characters which can draw meanings by readers are used indirectly to get the aim of the novel.”

To understand and feel the aim by readers, the writer uses eagerly literacy techniques indirectly. It is found that the writer composes the novel by using skill of plot creation to be interesting in the novella: “A Recommendation Letter”.

2.1 Plot Creation Techniques

In plot creation techniques, Sayar Zaw Gyi, Burmese poet, said there are exposition, rising action, Climax, Falling action, and resolution. Regarding with plot creation techniques, it is said that there are five stages in creating of the writer, and five stages in readers’ mindfulness.

In the novellas called “A Recommendation Letter”, the exposition is the event in which arriving for worship to the mother’s death when the main character knows about it. Due to this event, remorse and realization is attained when he has arrived the village for recommendation to receive inheritance, and last will and testament. He donated a building with his mother’s name for welfare of the community and also relinquished his bad habit, gambling. These scenes are not created specially and deliberately to attract readers’ attention but they are created by simple events with retrospective technique.

Characteristics of the good plot was studied and presented by Gustar Freytag in 1863. His presentation was in the form of pyramid. They are exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, and resolution. In the novels, these characteristics were fully equipped. In the novellas, it may contain all of these five characteristics, and some may not contain all. In this novella named “A Recommendation Letter”, it can be seen containing all five characteristics of plot structure.

Figure 1: Gustar Freytag's Plot Structure

3.2 Sequencing

The plot contains the nature of sequences. It is about connecting prior event and later event logically. Thus, readers can understand logical sequences of the upcoming events while they are reading novels.

Regarding to logical sequencing for events in the plot, Xu said that –

“Plot is written by sequencing events logically. Each event is arising as the effect of previous event which is because of the principles like possibility and necessity. Likewise, the late events in the novel are arising according to the principles.”

Events must be logically connected. It can be said that the late events are possibilities and related necessities of the previous ones. It is revealed that events are relatively pragmatic and richly natural since they are created by sequencing.

3.3 Composition in Detail

Writers also compose their fine arts in detail in order to absorb their readers' interests. The art known as composition in detail is writing detail about plot, characters, time, and background. The writer composes the (body, mind, soul) manners in line with readers, and background in order to clearly describe in the mind of readers. By creating like this, the readers accept that it is credible like real episode and feel in the flow of the novel. The composition in detail supports the readers' acceptability on the characters' real occurrences and events in the mind of readers. Being natural and likable pleasure can attain from feeling like realistic texture on the events.

The novella named “A Recommendation Letter” is the writing about prioritizing on the social life problem. Composition in detail is created symmetrically with short scenes. By writing in detail, appearance and traits of character in social life problems draw the attention of readers.

Discussion

The novella named “A Recommendation Letter” was written in 2010, and it reflects vividly social life problem. It can be seen the novella is created effectively by plot creations, plot structure, sequencing, and composition in detail.

In the choice of story, the topic is every day matter which happens in actual life.

In order to draw attention from readers, every stage of plot structure, which is plot creating skill, is fully depicted by the writer. (What special is all stages of plot structure can be rarely seen in a novella.) It can be seen that being obvious in natural in terms of sequencing, and feeling pleasure and being interested to readers in terms of composition in detail are effectively employed.

Conclusion

This paper examines about plot creation skill in novellas of the current period. In part of plot creation, flaws can be found. However, it is revealed that plot creation skill in this novella can be regarded as having the capability of drawing readers’ attention throughout the periods.

References

- Xu (Writer). (2010) “*A Recommendation Letter*”
- Gyi, Z. (1981) *Introduction of Novel Papers*. Vol.1, Yangon, Sar Pae Beik Man Press. Pg 12-13.
- Gyi, Z. (1994) *Introduction of Aesthetic Literature*. 2nd Published. Yangon. Seik Ku Cho Cho Publication.
- Toe, T. (1961) *Literature and Life*. Yangon. Nu Yin Publication.
- Ta, T. K. N. (1957). *If you want to write novel,...* . Yangon. Nway Win Sandar Magazine.
- Myint, T. (1969). *All Stories of A Writer’s Life*. Yangon. Than Lwin Publication.
- Colwell, C.C. (1968). *A Student’s Guide to Literature*. New York. Washington Square Press.
- Morner, K. & Rausch, R. (1998). *NTC’s Dictionary of Literary Terms*. USA. NTC Publishing Group.
- Peck, J. & Coyle, M. (1985). *Literary Terms and Criticism*. London, Macmillian Education Ltd.

Nan San Htwe (Liu Zhimei), born in 20th November, 1973, get the first B.A. Chemistry(Mandalay University) in 30th October,1999 and then completed M.A. Chinese(Mandalay University of Foreign Languages) in 12th January,2016. Mini-novels are the ones that can acknowledge people and make them relax. As I am a person who approach Chinese Language and culture, this mini-novels help me a lot in learning. Among them, short novels written by Myanmar-born Chinese are the best for me and therefore, I do this research and I believe this will help many people ,who are learning Chinese Language ,to get the ideas what to read to be more proficient.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Assets of publishing with NAAR

- Global archiving of articles
- Immediate, free online access for all
- Rigorous peer review process
- Authors retain copyrights
- DOI for all articles

<https://twasp.info/journal/home>

The graphic features a green globe with a plant growing from it, set against a background of radiating lines.

Submit your article : editor@twasp.info